

ГІНЕКОЛОГІЧНІ ЗАХВОРЮВАННЯ В АНАМНЕЗІ, ЯК ПЕРЕДУМОВИ РИЗИКІВ ПЕРЕДЧАСНИХ ПОЛОГІВ (ПБ)

GYNECOLOGICAL DISEASES IN THE ANAMNESIS AS PREREQUISITES FOR THE RISKS OF PREMATURE BIRTH (PB)

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Premature pregnancy is one of the most pressing problems of modern perinatal medicine. In 22-27 weeks, PB is caused by the infection of the lower pole of the amniotic sac and its premature rupture, bacterial vaginosis, and isthmio-cervical insufficiency.

The purpose of the study is to assess the role and significance of gynecological diseases and determine their impact on the risk of PB.

The total cohort the examined consisted of 150 pregnant women who met the criteria and requirements of the purpose of the study and gave their consent to participate in the study. The pregnant women received the necessary treatment at Lviv Regional Clinical Perinatal Center. The following research methods were used in the examination of the pregnant women: questionnaire-anamnestic, laboratory, general-clinical, mathematical-statistical.

Among the cohort of the examined pregnant women (150) PB was confirmed in 53 cases (35.3%), during the gestation period of 24-32 weeks. The 97 pregnant women (64.7%) gave birth to babies in the usual time. Risk assessment was performed by taking into account socio-economic reasons, the assessment of the presence/absence of bad habits, the presence of benign tumors, and the analysis of the consequences of previous pregnancies, and inflammatory gynecological diseases in the anamnesis.

The etiological risk factors for the development of PB include low socio-economic standard of living; mother's age <18 and> 35 years; smoking, drug addiction, stress; premature birth in the anamnesis; the abnormalities of uterine development; barrenness; abortions; multifetal pregnancy; bleeding during pregnancy; chorioamnionitis; isthmio-cervical insufficiency; asymptomatic bacteriuria; bacterial vaginosis in women with premature birth in the anamnesis.

According to the questionnaire-anamnestic studies, it was stated that the dominant risk factors for PB in pregnant women included in the study were as follows: socio-economic reasons (11;7.3% of cases); the pathology of the cervix (7;4.7%), the chronic inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs (6;4%), treatment for benign tumors

of the pelvic organs (13;8.7%), treatment by gynecologists for primary (13;8.7%) and secondary infertility (3;2%).

The analysis shows that gynecological diseases in the anamnesis may be a prerequisite for the threat of PB in 28% of pregnant women, and socio-economic causes, respectively, in 7.3%.

Preventive measures that reduce the risk of PB should include the assessment of the degree of the forecast risk of the development of maternal and perinatal pathology to determine the level of inpatient care; the prevention of respiratory distress syndrome up to 34 weeks of pregnancy; monitoring the condition of the mother and the fetus during childbirth.